

PALB2: CanVIG-UK Gene-Specific Guidance

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A. Garrett^{1,2}, S. Allen¹, L. Loong¹, M Durkie³, G.J. Burghe^{4,5}, R. Robinson⁶, A. Callaway⁷, J. Field⁸, B. Frugtriet², S. Palmer-Smith⁹, J. Grant¹⁰, J. Pagan¹¹, T. McDevitt¹², L. Hughes¹³, K. Snape², T. McVeigh¹⁴, H. Hanson^{15,16}, C. Turnbull^{1,14}

1. Division of Genetics and Epidemiology, The Institute of Cancer Research, London, UK.
2. St George's University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, Tooting, London, UK
3. North East and Yorkshire Genomic Laboratory Hub, Sheffield Children's NHS Foundation Trust, Sheffield, UK
4. Division of Cancer Sciences, School of Medical Sciences, Faculty of Biology, Medicine and Health, The University of Manchester, Manchester, UK
5. Manchester Centre for Genomic Medicine and NW Laboratory Genetics Hub, Manchester University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, Manchester, UK
6. The Leeds Genetics Laboratory, NEY Genomic Laboratory Hub, Leeds Teaching Hospitals NHS Trust, Leeds, UK
7. Central and South Genomics Laboratory Hub, Wessex Genomics Laboratory Service, University Hospital Southampton NHS Foundation Trust, Salisbury, UK.
8. Genomics and Molecular Medicine Service, Nottingham University Hospitals NHS Trust, Nottingham, UK
9. Wales Genomic Health Centre, Cardiff and Vale University Health Board, Cardiff, UK
10. Laboratory Genetics, Queen Elizabeth University Hospital, NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde, Glasgow, UK
11. South East Scotland Clinical Genetics, Western General Hospital, Edinburgh, UK.
12. Department of Clinical Genetics, CHI at Crumlin, Dublin, Ireland
13. West Midlands Genomics Laboratory, Birmingham Women's and Children's NHS Foundation Trust, Birmingham, UK
14. The Royal Marsden NHS Foundation Trust, Fulham Road, London
15. Peninsula Regional Genetics Service, Royal Devon University Healthcare NHS Foundation Trust, Exeter, UK
16. Department of Clinical and Biomedical Sciences, University of Exeter Medical School, Exeter, United Kingdom

CanVIG-UK review of PALB2: Consensus to use relevant recommendations from the ClinGen Hereditary Breast, Ovarian and Pancreatic Cancer Expert Panel Specifications to the ACMG/AMP Variant Interpretation Guidelines for PALB2 Version 1.2.0 (available at: <https://clinicalgenome.org/affiliation/50039/>, PDF attached below) for PALB2 variants reported under indication R208 of the UK Genomic Test Directory. Additional points of specification are given below where applicable.

Summary: Evidence towards Pathogenicity

Evidence element	Evidence strengths allowed				Use as per VCEP	Additional clarifications/thresholds/data-sources
PVS1	_VSTR	_STR	_MOD	_SUP	✓	
PS1		_STR	_MOD	_SUP	✓	
PS2					✓	
PS3					✓	
PS4		_STR			✓	From CanVIG-UK: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There should be a minimum of 2 case observations before PS4 can be applied. • Female-only population controls are recommended for use. • See main CanVIG-UK consensus specification for database recommendations.
PM1					✓	
PM2				_SUP	✓	From CanVIG-UK: Use <u>female-only</u> population controls
PM3	_VSTR	_STR	_MOD	_SUP	✓	
PM4					✓	
PM5				_SUP	✓	
PP1		_STR	_MOD	_SUP	✓	
PP2					✓	
PP3				_SUP	✓	
PP4					✓	

Summary: Evidence towards Benignity

BA1/BS1	_SA	_STR			✓	From CanVIG-UK: Use <u>female-only</u> population controls
BS2		_STR	_MOD	_SUP	✓	
BS3					✓	
BS4		_STR	_MOD	_SUP	✓	

BP1				_SUP	✓	
BP2						✓
BP3						✓
BP4				_SUP	✓	
BP5						✓
BP7		_STR	_MOD	_SUP	✓	

Version History/Amendments

Revised version	Date	Section	Update	Amended by	Approved by
1.0	02/06/2023	--	Initial Version	--	
1.1	04/08/2023	PM2	Specified to use female-only sex matched controls.	Allen	CStAG
1.1	30/10/2023	PS4	Requirement for a minimum of 2 case observations and female-only sex matched controls.	Garrett	CStAG
1.2	25/01/2024	Top of page	Statement updated to confirm this guidance should follow the VCEP PALB2 guidance v1.1.0	Allen	CStAG
1.2	25/01/2024	BP4	Evidence criteria allowed as per VCEP	Allen	CStAG
1.2	25/01/2024	BA1/BS1	Specified to use female-only sex matched controls.	Allen	CStAG
1.3	07/10/2025	PP5	Removed code as no longer in use	Allen	CStAG
1.3	07/10/2025	Statement	Update to reference current VCEP version (v1.4.0)	Allen	CStAG

ClinGen Hereditary Breast, Ovarian and Pancreatic Cancer Expert Panel Specifications to the ACMG/AMP Variant Interpretation Guidelines for PALB2 Version 1.2.0

Affiliation: Hereditary Breast, Ovarian and Pancreatic Cancer VCEP

Type: Richards et.al., 2015 - Combining rules

Description : Summary of ACMG-AMP Criteria for PALB2 (autosomal dominant and autosomal recessive disorders)

Version : 1.2.0

Released : 7/14/2025

Release Notes :

Release notes v1.2

Provided % for PM2 and clarified use of gnomAD v4

Clarified when to assume in trans for PM3

Provided PP1 guidance for AR condition

Added SpliceAI thresholds for PP3 and BP4

Clarified use of PP3/BP4 in the presence of RNA data

Updated MONDO from hereditary breast carcinoma and familial pancreatic carcinoma to PALB2-related cancer predisposition

Minor formatting adjustments

Rules for PALB2

General Comments: Release notes v1.2 Provided % for PM2 and clarified use of gnomAD v4 Clarified when to assume in trans for PM3 Provided PP1 guidance for AR condition Added SpliceAI thresholds for PP3 and BP4 Clarified use of PP3/BP4 in the presence of RNA data Updated MONDO from hereditary breast carcinoma and familial pancreatic carcinoma to PALB2-related cancer predisposition PVS1 clarification for last nucleotide of exon Minor formatting adjustments

Gene: PALB2 (HGNC:26144) [↗](#)

Transcripts:

NM_024675.3

HGNC Name: partner and localizer of BRCA2

Disease:

PALB2-related cancer predisposition

(MONDO:0700272) [↗](#) **Mode**

of Inheritance: Autosomal dominant inheritance

Fanconi anemia

complementation group N

(MONDO:0012565) [↗](#) **Mode**

of Inheritance: Autosomal recessive inheritance

Criteria & Strength Specifications

PVS1

Original ACMG

Summary

Null variant (nonsense, frameshift, canonical ± 1 or 2 splice sites, initiation codon, single or multi-exon deletion) in a gene where loss of function (LOF) is a known mechanism of disease.

Caveats:

- Beware of genes where LOF is not a known disease mechanism (e.g. GFAP, MYH7).
- Use caution interpreting LOF variants at the extreme 3' end of a gene.
- Use caution with splice variants that are predicted to lead to exon skipping but leave the remainder of the protein intact.
- Use caution in the presence of multiple transcripts.

VCEP

Specifications:

- Use PALB2 PVS1 Decision Tree Per PALB2 Exon Map and PALB2 PVS1 Guide
- PVS1: Predicted splice defect
- PVS1_Strength(RNA): Observed splice defect
- The default RefSeq transcript for nucleotide (c.) annotation is NM_024675.3/ENST00000261584.8. Several naturally occurring alternate splicing isoforms have been described¹. Yet, after careful examination, none of them is considered a candidate rescue transcript (very low contribution to overall expression, not coding proteins predicted functional, or both). In keeping with that, we have considered that all presumed LoF events (PVS1 decision tree specifications) occur in biologically relevant transcript(s).
- WD40 beta propeller and the Coiled-coil domain (CC) are considered indispensable for PALB2 protein function.
 - PVS1 alterations that are predicted to escape NMD, but that adversely affect the WD40 domain can be granted PVS1 (as opposed to PVS1_Strong as the recommended baseline²). The following evidence supports this strength change:
 - The WD40 domain interacts with many different protein partners that are involved in the double strand break repair pathway³
 - Two different C-terminal truncating mutations (c.3549C>A and c.3549C>G) resulting in loss of the last 3 amino acids [p. (Tyr1183Ter)], were identified in trans with PALB2 stop-gain variants in three unrelated FA (FA-N) patients⁴
 - The PALB2 WD40 toroidal structure is “sealed” in the seventh blade by interaction of the C-terminal strand with the incomplete N-terminal blade. The last four residues of PALB2 (Y1183, H1184, Y1185, and S1186) are directly involved in this interaction (molecular Velcro hydrogen bonding)¹⁵. This is the rationale for the clinical relevance of the last 4 amino acids of the protein.

- Alterations predicted to lead to in frame losses adversely affecting the WD40 structure/function are found in trans with LoF PALB2 alterations in Fanconi Anemia patients⁴
 - Exon 10 donor: c.3113+5G>C (biallelic with c.395delT)
 - Exon 12 donor: c.3350+4A>G (biallelic with c.2393_2394insCT)
- LoF alterations are rare in GnomAD in all exons
 - GnomAD v2.1 accessed 5/30/2019
 - Total Variants (includes splice acceptor/donor-conservative)
 - 1418 variants
 - 336,349 carriers
 - LoF Flag (excludes splice acceptor/donor-conservative)
 - 95 variants (6.7%)
 - 239 carriers (.07%)
- PVS1 can be applied as per the PVS1 decision tree.
 - PVS1_Variable(RNA) shall be used for observed splice defects, whether from canonical +/-1,2 positions or other spliceogenic regions (including mid-exonic missense/synonymous variants that cause splice defects) with baseline weight as per the below decision tree. Weight can be further modified based on the quality of the RNA study including consideration of concepts such as:
 - Starting material (where patient material is preferable to in vitro minigene)
 - Use of NMD inhibitors where translation does occur such as cell lines⁵⁶
 - Primer design (to make sure it's comprehensive to capture possible multicassette events)
 - Method of quantification
 - where e.g. capillary electrophoresis is preferable to estimation by gel band density
 - where SNP analysis is most preferred (where analysis of exonic SNPs and their relative presence in aberrant and WT transcripts is informative)
 - Quantification (where complete effects should have increased weight over incomplete effects)
 - Specific guidance on the use of RNA evidence in variant assessment is not a gene-specific consideration for PALB2 at this time, therefore discretion is left to assessors until further guidance is provided for this general concept from the Sequence Variant Interpretation group.
- In the event that RNA data are available and they reflect a substantial variant-specific impact, do not use both PVS1(RNA) and PP3 or BP4. However, in the event that RNA data are available and

they reflect no variant-specific impacts, PP3 or BP4 may be applied in conjunction with BP7(RNA).

Very Strong

Use PALB2 PVS1 Decision Tree

Modification Gene-specific,Strength

Type:

Strong

Use PALB2 PVS1 Decision Tree.

Modification Gene-specific,Strength

Type:

Moderate

Use PALB2 PVS1 Decision Tree.

Modification Gene-specific,Strength

Type:

Supporting

Use PALB2 PVS1 Decision Tree

Modification Gene-specific,Strength

Type:

PS1

Original ACMG

Summary

Same amino acid change as a previously established pathogenic variant regardless of nucleotide change.

Example: Val->Leu caused by either G>C or G>T in the same codon.

Caveat: Beware of changes that impact splicing rather than at the amino acid/protein level.

VCEP

Specifications:

- Missense: Do not use. Missense changes are not yet confirmed as a mechanism of disease for PALB2
- Splicing: See PALB2 PS1 Table (PMID: 37352859)

Strong

Use PALB2 PS1 Splicing table

Modification General recommendation

Type:

Moderate

Use PALB2 PS1 Splicing table

Modification General recommendation

Type:

Supporting

Use PALB2 PS1 Splicing table

Modification General recommendation

Type:

PS2

Original ACMG

Summary

De novo (both maternity and paternity confirmed) in a patient with the disease and no family history.

Note: Confirmation of paternity only is insufficient. Egg donation, surrogate motherhood, errors in embryo transfer, etc. can contribute to non-maternity.

Not Applicable

Comments: Do not use for AD or AR disease: Informative de novo occurrences have not yet been observed and de novo AR conditions are unlikely to be informed by phase ● Autosomal Dominant Disease: Do not use - Informative de novo occurrences have not yet been observed for autosomal dominant disease. As breast cancer is relatively common and occurs frequently as an apparently sporadic event, de novo is unlikely to ever be informative unless specific features of PALB2-related cancer predisposition are identified. ● Autosomal Recessive Disease: Do not use - de novo occurrences are too rare to be informative at this time. In addition, in a biallelic state, de novo occurrences have an exceedingly low probability of being able to be confirmed as in trans because parental testing (and identification of one variant in each parent) is typically required without the use of long-range technologies.

PS3

Original ACMG

Summary

Well-established in vitro or in vivo functional studies supportive of a damaging effect on the gene or gene product.

Note: Functional studies that have been validated and shown to be reproducible and robust in a clinical diagnostic laboratory setting are considered the most well-established.

Not Applicable

Comments: ● Protein: Do not use: Lack of known positive controls ● RNA: Do not use:
See code PVS1_Variable(RNA)

PS4

Original ACMG Summary

The prevalence of the variant in affected individuals is significantly increased compared to the prevalence in controls.

Note 1: Relative risk (RR) or odds ratio (OR), as obtained from case-control studies, is >5.0 and the confidence interval around the estimate of RR or OR does not include 1.0.

See manuscript for detailed guidance.

Note 2: In instances of very rare variants where case-control studies may not reach statistical significance, the prior observation of the variant in multiple unrelated patients with the same phenotype, and its absence in controls, may be used as moderate level of evidence.

VCEP Specifications PS4_Moderate: Do not use. Proband counting for genes causing a common disorder need to be calibrated in a population-specific way before use.

Strong

Case-control studies; p-value $\leq .05$ AND (Odds ratio, hazard ratio, or relative risk ≥ 3 OR lower 95% CI ≥ 1.5).

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

PM1

Original ACMG Summary

Located in a mutational hot spot and/or critical and well-established functional domain (e.g. active site of an enzyme) without benign variation.

Not Applicable

Comments: Do not use: Missense pathogenic variation in PALB2 is not yet confirmed as a mechanism of disease.

PM2

Original ACMG Summary

Absent from controls (or at extremely low frequency if recessive) in Exome Sequencing Project, 1000 Genomes or Exome Aggregation Consortium.

Caveat: Population data for indels may be poorly called by next generation sequencing.

VCEP

- EXCEPTION: under-represented sub-populations with n=1 but

Specifications:

frequency >.0003%

- Is not considered a conflicting piece of evidence for variants that otherwise are likely benign/benign
- Use as **PM2_Supporting** (not moderate)

Supporting

Frequency \leq 1/300,000 (**0.000333%**) in gnomAD v4 dataset

Modification Gene-specific, Strength

Type:

PM3**Original ACMG****Summary**

For recessive disorders, detected in trans with a pathogenic variant

Note: This requires testing of parents (or offspring) to determine phase.

VCEP

See **Fanconi Anemia PM3 tables** for approach to assign points per

Specifications proband, and final PM3 code assignment based on the sum of PM3-related points.

Fanconi Anemia (FA) of any subtype is generally considered an exceedingly rare, severe, early-onset disease with variable features. In the case of *BRCA2*, hypomorphic FA patients have been described who are diagnosed at older ages with less severe phenotypes. The criteria set forth in the tables below are designed to accommodate such hypomorphs and are recommended to be applied to all FA-associated genes which may not be as well described due to the extreme infrequency of their identification, and due to ascertainment bias (for severe phenotype) in the literature.

- General Considerations
 - Variant may not exceed general population frequency >0.01%.
 - Consider other gene panel test results as potential explanation for phenotype.
 - Multiple unrelated cases are additive.

Phenotype consistent:

- Chromosomal breakage with 1 clinical feature OR
 - Ex. Chromosomal breakage testing + microcephaly / triangular face
- At least 2 of 3 clinical features from separate categories without chromosomal breakage studies
 - Ex. (Without chromosomal breakage): Myelodysplastic Syndrome and microcephaly / triangular face.

- Positive for chromosome breakage test:
 - Increased chromosome breakage and/or radial forms on cytogenetic testing of lymphocytes with diepoxybutane (DEB) or mitomycin C (MMC)
- Clinical features indicative of FA, including
 - Physical features (in ~75% of affected persons), include:
 - prenatal and/or postnatal short stature
 - abnormal skin pigmentation (e.g., café au lait macules, hypo- pigmentation)
 - Skeletal malformations (e.g., hypoplastic thumb, hypoplastic radius)
 - Microcephaly, triangular face
 - Ophthalmic anomalies
 - Genitourinary tract anomalies.
 - See Orphanet ¹³ for full list of >100 HPO terms (and their reported frequency).
 - Pathology findings and laboratory findings (non-cancer related) include
 - progressive bone marrow failure (unrelated to cancer treatment)
 - aplastic anemia
 - Myelodysplastic syndrome
 - Inordinate toxicities from chemotherapy or radiation
 - macrocytosis
 - cytopenia (especially thrombocytopenia, leukopenia, and neutropenia)
 - increased fetal hemoglobin (often precedes anemia).
 - Note: FA patients with very early onset cancer (≤ 5 yr) may not present with hematologic disease, which is reported to have median age at onset of 7 years in FA patients in general¹⁴
 - Cancer diagnosis ≤ 5 yr, particularly
 - Blood cancers (AML)
 - Brain cancers (medulloblastoma, neuroblastoma)
 - Wilms Tumor

Specifications are adapted from definitions from GeneReviews (last revision June 3, 2021)

Very Strong

PM3_VeryStrong ≥ 8 points

See Fanconi Anemia PM3 tables for approach to assign points per proband.

Modification Disease-specific, Strength

Type:

Strong

PM3_Strong \geq 4 points

See Fanconi Anemia PM3 tables for approach to assign points per proband.

Modification Disease-specific, Strength

Type:

Moderate

PM3 = 2 points

See Fanconi Anemia PM3 tables for approach to assign points per proband.

Modification Disease-specific, Strength

Type:

Supporting

PM3_Supporting = 1 point

See Fanconi Anemia PM3 tables for approach to assign points per proband.

Modification Disease-specific, Strength

Type:

PM4

Original ACMG

Summary

Protein length changes due to in-frame deletions/insertions in a non-repeat region or stop-loss variants.

Not Applicable

Comments: Do not use: ● In-frame deletions/insertions that are not already PVS1-eligible: no information is available to justify the application of this rule. ● Missense and small in-frame indels: not yet confirmed as a mechanism of disease for PALB2. ● Stop-loss: lack of data on stop-loss variants.

PM5

Original ACMG

Summary

Novel missense change at an amino acid residue where a different missense change determined to be pathogenic has been seen before.

Example: Arg156His is pathogenic; now you observe Arg156Cys.

Caveat: Beware of changes that impact splicing rather than at the amino acid/protein level.

VCEP

- Based on location of the most C-terminal known pathogenic variant,

Specifications: p.Tyr1183*.

- Use as **PM5_Supporting** (not moderate)
- Do not use for missense changes: Missense changes are not yet confirmed as a mechanism of disease for PALB2.

Supporting

- Apply to frameshifting or truncating variants with premature termination codons upstream of p.Tyr1183.
- Apply to splice variants as with premature termination codons upstream of p.Tyr1183 where PVS1_VS(RNA) is applied based on high quality observed splicing impact and must be NMD prone.

Modification Gene-specific,Strength**Type:****PM6****Original ACMG****Summary**

Assumed de novo, but without confirmation of paternity and maternity.

Not Applicable

Comments: Do not use for AD or AR disease: Informative de novo occurrences have not yet been observed and de novo AR conditions are unlikely to be informed by phase

PP1**Original ACMG****Summary**

Co-segregation with disease in multiple affected family members in a gene definitively known to cause the disease.

Note: May be used as stronger evidence with increasing segregation data.

VCEP**Specifications:**

- AD Condition: use as per Co-Segregation Guidelines
- AR Condition: Affected relatives must have both variants identified in proband.
- Co-Segregation Guidelines
 - Quantitative co-segregation analysis is mandated for more accurate assessment of causality for PALB2 alterations. It is strongly preferred that biocurators use a quantitative method that accommodates both pathologies of AD PALB2: breast cancer, ovarian cancer and pancreatic cancer. These methods may be conducted by biostatisticians, particularly if they are able to compute LR scores⁹ using multiple phenotypes.

- PP1_Strong: LOD ≥ 1.26 or Bayes Factor (LR) $\geq 18:1$
 - PP1_Moderate: LOD $\geq .60$ or Bayes Factor (LR) $\geq 4:1$
 - PP1: LOD ≥ 0.3 or Bayes Factor (LR) $\geq 2:18$
 - BS4_Supporting: LOD $\leq -.32$ or Bayes Factor (LR) $\leq .48$
 - BS4_Moderate: LOD $\leq -.64$ or Bayes Factor (LR) $\leq .23$
 - BS4: LOD ≤ -1.28 or Bayes Factor (LR) $LR \leq .053:1$
- A freely available tool, COOL (COsegregation OnLine) from Bing-Jian Feng's laboratory can be used to calculate LoD scores for co-segregation analysis
 1. Navigate to COOL (COsegregation OnLine)⁷
 2. Input 'PALB2' into the 'Input a Gene Symbol' field (the PALB2 defaults are approved by this VCEP)
 3. Upload your Pedigree File (see COOL (COsegregation OnLine) manual⁸ for formatting)
 4. Leave all defaults as is. Select 'Submit' to obtain LR based on Full Likelihood Bayes (FLB)

Strong

- AD Condition: LOD ≥ 1.26 or Bayes Factor (LR) $\geq 18:1$
- AR Condition: Segregation in ≥ 3 affected relatives

Modification Gene-specific

Type:

Moderate

- AD Condition: LOD $\geq .60$ or Bayes Factor (LR) $\geq 4:1$
- AR Condition: Segregation in 2 affected relatives

Modification Gene-specific

Type:

Supporting

- AD Condition: LOD ≥ 0.3 or Bayes Factor (LR) $\geq 2:1$
- AR Condition: Segregation in 1 affected relative

Modification Gene-specific

Type:

PP2

Original ACMG Summary

Missense variant in a gene that has a low rate of benign missense variation and where missense variants are a common mechanism of disease.

Not Applicable

Comments: Do not use. Missense is not yet confirmed or refuted as a mechanism of disease for PALB2

PP3

Original ACMG Summary

Multiple lines of computational evidence support a deleterious effect on the gene or gene product (conservation, evolutionary, splicing impact, etc.).

Caveat: As many in silico algorithms use the same or very similar input for their predictions, each algorithm should not be counted as an independent criterion. PP3 can be used only once in any evaluation of a variant.

VCEP

Specifications:

- So far, published predictors have yet to achieve functional outcome for PALB2 missense variants
- NOTE: Splice analysis needs to be considered for all variant types (including missense, frameshift, nonsense, etc. as any variant has the potential to impact splicing which may preclude any expected protein effects)
- NOTE: PP3 for splice predictions may not be applied in addition to PVS1 or PVS1_Variable(RNA) codes.
- Use caution in applying the wrong type of computational evidence (protein vs. RNA) towards the cumulative body of evidence for the opposite mechanism.
- The VCEP uses SpliceAI as a sole predictor due to its ability to accurately predict loss of native splice sites and creation of cryptic sites (Jaganathan et al., 2019). This VCEP recommends SpliceAI thresholds set forth by the SVI in applying PP3 and BP4 to non-canonical splice variants: Apply PP3 for SpliceAI scores ≥ 0.2 and apply BP4 for SpliceAI scores ≤ 0.1 (Walker et al., 2023).
- In the event that RNA data are available and they reflect a substantial variant-specific impact, do not use both PVS1(RNA) and PP3 or BP4. However, in the event that RNA data are available and they reflect no variant-specific impacts, PP3 or BP4 may be applied in conjunction with BP7(RNA).

Supporting

- Missense: Do not use.
- Splicing: Predicted impact via splicing (SpliceAI ≥ 0.2) for silent, missense/in-frame and for intronic variants outside of donor and acceptor 1,2 sites.

Modification General recommendation

Type:

PP4

Original ACMG

Summary

Patient's phenotype or family history is highly specific for a disease with a single genetic etiology.

Not Applicable

Comments: Do not use for AD disorder as breast cancer is a disease with multiple genetic etiology (genetic heterogeneity) and there are no features that can readily distinguish hereditary from sporadic causes. For AR disorder, use PM3 for specific phenotype considerations

PP5

Original ACMG

Summary

Reputable source recently reports variant as pathogenic, but the evidence is not available to the laboratory to perform an independent evaluation.

Not Applicable

This criterion is not for use as recommended by the ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation VCEP Review Committee. [PubMed : 29543229](#)

BA1

Original ACMG

Summary

Allele frequency is above 5% in Exome Sequencing Project, 1000 Genomes or Exome Aggregation Consortium.

VCEP Specifications: Follow all [SVI general guidance](#) on applying population filters.

Stand Alone

Grpmax Filtering AF **>.1%** in gnomAD v4 dataset

Modification Type: Disease-specific, Gene-specific

BS1

Original ACMG

Summary

Allele frequency is greater than expected for disorder.

VCEP Specifications: Follow all [SVI general guidance](#) on applying population filters.

Strong

Grpmax Filtering AF **>.01%** in gnomAD v4 dataset

Modification Disease-specific, Gene-specific

Type:

BS2

Original ACMG

Summary

Observed in a healthy adult individual for a recessive (homozygous), dominant (heterozygous), or X-linked (hemizygous) disorder, with full penetrance expected at an early age.

VCEP

See **Fanconi Anemia BS2 tables** for approach to assign points per proband, and final BS2 code assignment based on the sum of BS2-related points.

- Do not use for individuals in population based cohorts, such as gnomAD
- VUA should not be bioinformatically predicted (or experimentally proven) to have a clinically important effect on protein or mRNA splicing. Co-occurrent P or LP variant should be assigned classification using VCEP specifications
- Consider multiple instances of co-occurrence with the same variant are more likely to be in cis in unrelated individuals when assessing BS2 application

Strong

BS2 \geq **4** points

See Fanconi Anemia BS2 tables for approach to assign points per proband.

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

Moderate

BS2_Moderate = **2** points

See Fanconi Anemia BS2 tables for approach to assign points per proband.

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

Supporting

BS2_Supporting = **1** point

See Fanconi Anemia BS2 tables for approach to assign points per proband.

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

BS3

Original ACMG

Summary

Well-established in vitro or in vivo functional studies show no damaging effect on protein function or splicing.

Not Applicable

Comments: Do not use: ● Protein functional studies (BS3) See PS3 for details ● RNA functional studies (Use BP7_Variable(RNA))

BS4

Original ACMG

Summary

Lack of segregation in affected members of a family.

Caveat: The presence of phenocopies for common phenotypes (i.e. cancer, epilepsy) can mimic lack of segregation among affected individuals. Also, families may have more than one pathogenic variant contributing to an autosomal dominant disorder, further confounding an apparent lack of segregation.

VCEP

Specifications:

- Quantitative co-segregation analysis is mandated for more accurate assessment of causality for PALB2 alterations. It is strongly preferred that biocurators use a quantitative method that accommodates both pathologies of AD PALB2: breast cancer, ovarian cancer and pancreatic cancer. These methods may be conducted by biostatisticians, particularly if they are able to compute LR scores⁹ using multiple phenotypes.
 - PP1_Strong: LOD ≥ 1.26 or Bayes Factor (LR) $\geq 18:1$
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manual¹² for formatting)

4. Leave all defaults as is. Select 'Submit' to obtain LR based on Full Likelihood Bayes (FLB)

Strong

LOD \leq -1.28 or Bayes Factor (LR) \leq .053:1

Modification Gene-specific

Type:

Moderate

LOD \leq -.64 or Bayes Factor (LR) \leq .23

Modification Gene-specific

Type:

Supporting

LOD \leq -.32 or Bayes Factor (LR) \leq .48

Modification Gene-specific

Type:

BP1

Original ACMG

Summary

Missense variant in a gene for which primarily truncating variants are known to cause disease.

VCEP

Based on published and unpublished functional studies, PALB2 has a low rate of missense variants that are non-functional in relevant assays. True missense pathogenic variants are not yet confirmed or refuted but are thought to be exceedingly rare. Given the very low likelihood that missense variants are pathogenic, this rule applies to all missense variants in PALB2.

Supporting

Apply to all missense variants.

Modification Gene-specific

Type:

BP2

Original ACMG

Summary

Observed in trans with a pathogenic variant for a fully penetrant dominant gene/disorder or observed in cis with a pathogenic variant in any inheritance pattern.

Not Applicable

Comments: Do not use: See Fanconi Anemia BS2 table

BP3

Original ACMG Summary

In frame-deletions/insertions in a repetitive region without a known function.

Not Applicable

Comments: Do not use: small in-frame losses are neither confirmed nor refuted as a mechanism of pathogenicity for PALB2. In addition, PALB2 is not considered to have repetitive regions without known function

BP4

Original ACMG Summary

Multiple lines of computational evidence suggest no impact on gene or gene product (conservation, evolutionary, splicing impact, etc)

Caveat: As many in silico algorithms use the same or very similar input for their predictions, each algorithm cannot be counted as an independent criterion. BP4 can be used only once in any evaluation of a variant.

VCEP

Specifications:

- Missense: Do not use. So far, published predictors have yet to achieve functional outcome for PALB2 missense variants
- NOTE: Splice analysis needs to be considered for all variant types (including missense, frameshift, nonsense, etc. as any variant has the potential to impact splicing which may preclude any expected protein effects)
- NOTE: BP4 for splice predictions may not be applied in conjunction with BP7_Variable(RNA) (a lack of observed RNA defect)
- Use caution in applying the wrong type of computational evidence (protein vs. RNA) towards the cumulative body of evidence for the opposite mechanism.
- The VCEP uses SpliceAI as a sole predictor due to its ability to accurately predict loss of native splice sites and creation of cryptic sites (Jaganathan et al., 2019). This VCEP recommends SpliceAI thresholds set forth by the SVI in applying PP3 and BP4 to non-canonical splice variants: Apply PP3 for SpliceAI scores ≥ 0.2 and apply BP4 for SpliceAI scores ≤ 0.1 (Walker et al., 2023).

- In the event that RNA data are available and they reflect a substantial variant-specific impact, do not use both PVS1(RNA) and PP3 or BP4. However, in the event that RNA data are available and they reflect no variant-specific impacts, PP3 or BP4 may be applied in conjunction with BP7(RNA).

Supporting

- Missense: Do not use.
- Splicing: No predicted impact via splicing (SpliceAI ≤ 0.1). Do not apply for missense variants.

Modification General recommendation

Type:

BP5

Original ACMG Summary

Variant found in a case with an alternate molecular basis for disease.

Not Applicable

Comments: Do not use: Cases with multiple pathogenic variants have been observed with no noticeable difference in phenotype (e.g. BRCA1 and BRCA2). In addition, PALB2 has moderate penetrance and will naturally occur with other pathogenic variants more frequently due to higher tolerance/presence in the general population.

BP6

Original ACMG Summary

Reputable source recently reports variant as benign, but the evidence is not available to the laboratory to perform an independent evaluation.

Not Applicable

This criterion is not for use as recommended by the ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation VCEP Review Committee. [PubMed : 29543229](#)

BP7

Original ACMG Summary

A synonymous variant for which splicing prediction algorithms predict no impact to the splice consensus sequence nor the creation of a new splice site AND the nucleotide is not highly conserved.

VCEP

Specifications:

- BP7: Synonymous and deep intronic
 - Can be used for deep intronic variants beyond (but not including) +7 (donor) and -21 (acceptor)
 - May also apply BP4 to achieve Likely Benign
 - Is not considered a conflicting piece of evidence against a body of evidence supporting a pathogenic splice defect
- BP7_Variable(RNA): RNA functional studies
 - Lack of aberrant splice defect: Please see PVS1_Variable(RNA) section (above) for guidance on baseline weights and modifications of weight based on quality for RNA assays
 - In the event that RNA data are available and they reflect a substantial variant-specific impact, do not use both PVS1(RNA) and PP3 or BP4. However, in the event that RNA data are available and they reflect no variant-specific impacts, PP3 or BP4 may be applied in conjunction with BP7(RNA).

Strong

BP7_Strong(RNA): Observed lack of aberrant RNA defect for silent substitutions and intronic variants. Variable weight applied depending on curator discretion of assay quality.

Modification General recommendation

Type:

Moderate

BP7_Moderate(RNA): Observed lack of aberrant RNA defect for silent substitutions and intronic variants. Variable weight applied depending on curator discretion of assay quality.

Modification General recommendation

Type:

Supporting

- BP7: Use for synonymous and deep intronic variants defined as further than (but not including) +7 and further than (but not including) -21 at donor and acceptor sites, respectively.
- BP7(RNA): Observed lack of aberrant RNA defect for silent substitutions and intronic variants. Variable weight applied depending on curator discretion of assay quality.

Modification General recommendation

Type:

Rules for Combining Criteria

Pathogenic

1 Very Strong AND \geq 1 Strong

1 Very Strong AND \geq 2 Moderate

1 Very Strong AND 1 Moderate AND 1 Supporting

1 Very Strong AND ≥ 2 Supporting

≥ 2 Strong

1 Strong AND ≥ 3 Moderate

1 Strong AND 2 Moderate AND ≥ 2 Supporting

1 Strong AND 1 Moderate AND ≥ 4 Supporting

Likely Pathogenic

1 Very Strong AND 1 Moderate

1 Strong AND 1 Moderate

1 Strong AND ≥ 2 Supporting

≥ 3 Moderate

2 Moderate AND ≥ 2 Supporting

1 Moderate AND ≥ 4 Supporting

1 Very Strong (PVS1) AND 1 Supporting (PVS1_Supporting, PS1_Supporting, PM2_Supporting, PM3_Supporting, PM5_Supporting, PP1, PP3)

Benign

≥ 2 Strong

1 Stand Alone

Likely Benign

1 Strong AND 1 Supporting

≥ 2 Supporting

1 Strong (BS1, BS2, BS4, BP7_Strong)

Files & Images

ClinGen HBOP ACMG Specifications PALB2 version 1.2: [↓](#)

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